

NEW TECHNOLOGIES AS KEY COMPONENTS IN OPTICAL SYSTEMS

Which key fits into which lock?

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ABSTRACT

The development of optical systems has a very long tradition, and innovation in this field is accelerating. From an optical design perspective, for example, the use of free-form surfaces and adaptive optics is opening up new possibilities in the architecture and design of optical systems. One key for innovation is to understand the special features of new technologies including their limitations. We present an optical architecture using adaptive freeform optics to enable a new type of fluorescence microscopy.

KEYWORDS: Adaptive optics, Freeform surfaces, Light sheet microscopy

NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN OPTICAL SYSTEMS

The phases of the well-known Gartner Hype Cycle can also be seen in optics. The emergence of new technologies often gives rise to nonrealistic expectations. In practice, optical systems are not broadly dominated by freeform surfaces, gratings, aspheres, or adaptive elements. They often consist of spherical lenses and mirrors, only.

Figure 1: Hype Cycle for Emerging Tech [1]

But there are countless examples of unique solutions when the strengths of new technologies are used where they fit. It is important to understand the character of new technologies with their strengths and weaknesses. During system development, the most important requirements, dependencies and limitations must be worked out in the analysis of the task. When the strength of a technology overcomes a limitation in a specific task, particular innovations become possible.

Table 1: Selection of technologies and some established applications.

These are examples where former "emerging" technologies have reached the "plateau of productivity".

Component	Typical application
Aspherical surfaces	Camera lenses for mobile phones, photographic lenses, lithographic lenses, laser collimators.
Freeform surfaces	EUV-mirror-systems, TMA-Telescopes, HUD, Progressive glasses.
Adaptive elements	Displays and projection, adaptive microscopy and astronomy (focusing, aberration correction).
Diffractive elements	Spectrometers, HUD, color correction, beam splitting, beam combining, coupling optics for waveguides, beam shaping, optical testing (CGH).
GRIN	laser collimator, fibre-coupling, endoscopic systems.

LATTICE LIGHT SHEET MICROSCOPY (EXAMPLE)

Fluorescence microscopy is an established method for examining living cells. However, the light used for excitation potentially damages living cells. The concept of Light sheet microscopy addresses the problem of phototoxicity. But tolerances of standard sample preparation disturb the image quality. To overcome this limitations, the use of freeform surfaces and adaptive elements in the optical system has been essential. This presentation will outline the difficulties encountered in oblique optical imaging through a plane-parallel cover glass and how they were overcome.

Figure 2: Light sheet microscopy splits fluorescence excitation and detection into two separate light paths, allowing to generate an inherent optical section by exciting only fluorescence from the in-focus plane.[2]

Figure 3: Schematic of sample carrier and core optics module with excitation objective (1), meniscus lens (2) and detection objective with free-form optics (3). Examples show imaging without (A) and with adaptive aberration compensation (B)[2]

CONCLUSIONS

Emerging technologies or new components can overcome limitations of classical optical systems. “Hype cycle for emerging tech” shows that expectations often raises too fast. But normally an emerging technology can't solve all challenges. Understanding the problem and knowing the strengths of a technology are essential to find the right fitting. Lattice Light sheet Microscopy is an example how freeform technology, beam shaping and adaptive optics overcome photodamage in fluorescence microscopy of living cells.

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